

University of Khartoum

Open Access Institutional Repository Policies

Preamble

University of Khartoum mission is to serve Sudanese and universal communities via dissemination of knowledge on humanities, arts and applied sciences. This is to be carried out using digital technology and the internet as a medium. University of Khartoum Vice Chancellor issued the following policies on recommendation from the Digital Content Committee and based on Article 16 of University of Khartoum Act 1995:

1. Definitions

(a) In this policy, the following words and phrases shall have the following meanings:

- The university: University of Khartoum (U. of K.)
- The institutional repository (IR): University of Khartoum Institutional Repository (KhartoumSpace IR)
- Intellectual property: all works that fall under Article 2(8) of the agreement establishing the World Intellectual Property Organization (Amendment) 1979, which include: arts, science, artists achievements, phonograms, radio and TV programmes, all types of inventions, scientific discoveries, drawings, industrial models, patency's, trademarks, names, commercial brands, protection against illegal competition, every work that is a product of human intelligence in all industrial, scientific, artistic and arts.
- The committee: The Digital Content Committee (DCC)
- The department: The Digital Content Department (DC)

- Work/s: scientific papers and books, thesis (masters or Ph.D.) in all specialties including scientific, pedagogic, arts and all those covered under intellectual property definitions
- University affiliates: tenure staff members, fellows, academic staff on contract basis, external supervisors and evaluators, teaching assistants, undergraduate and postgraduate students.

Objectives of the repository and its regulations

2. The university seeks to produce and communicate its intellectual output internationally under the following regulations:
 - (a) All university affiliates should give the university a written permission to upload their works, previously approved by appropriate councils, into the IR. This is done by filling the non-exclusive agreement in appendix (1).
 - (b) Based on the given permission, the university publishes the scholarly work. This assignment is subject to a perpetual, irrevocable, worldwide, royalty-free, non-exclusive license in favour of the university to allow others to use that work for teaching and research and to reproduce and communicate it online for non-commercial purposes via the university's open access digital repository (KhartoumSpace IR).
 - (c) Final approved scholarly works should be submitted in a digital format, free of charge, to the department immediately after submission. The version of the scholarly work that the university will make available via its IR may be the published version (if the publisher agrees), the final post-peer review manuscript version or the pre-print (i.e. pre-peer review) version when rights are with the publisher. University of Khartoum will agree to third party publisher requested embargoes of 6 months or less (from date of publication by the third party publisher) on the publication of the manuscript via its IR.
 - (d) The university has the right to upload approved works in its IR
 - (e) The university has the right to refuse uploading a work that breaches the university mission, vision or objectives.

- (f) The university does not hold responsibility for incorrect information or mistakes in the uploaded work/s.
- 3. Regulations in Article (2) apply on all approved works which were prepared by authors during working for the university and after leaving it.
- 4. The committee will be under the direct supervision of the Deputy Vice Chancellor (DVC). They are responsible of application of the IR policies, solving disputes and presenting appropriate suggestions regarding it to the Vice Chancellor.

KhartoumSpace IR content

- 5. (1) The IR contain, in addition to M.Sc. and Ph. D abstracts and text, the following:
 - a) Peer reviewed papers
 - b) Books
 - c) Book chapters
 - d) Nationally and internationally presented conference presentations (papers and posters)
 - e) Peer reviewed artistic and architectural models
 - f) Scientific arts and artistic inventions
 - g) Historical documents, maps, unclassified documents
 - h) Unpublished scientific works

(2) The following will not be published in the IR:

- a) Scientific work/s of potential commercial importance
- b) Scientific works which contain confidential or protected material
- c) Prohibited works with culturally sensitive issues
- d) Scientific works where the promulgation would infringe a legal commitment by the university and/or the author and/or third parties

Data policy

- 6. (1) All works uploaded in the IR will be available open access and accessible via the IR website: www.KhartoumSpace IR.uofk.edu available for searching by engines such as

Google Scholar and the world catalogue project (OAIster, website: <http://oaister.worldcat.org>).

(2) Anyone can access uploaded works free of charge for research and training purposes without permission under the following regulations:

- (a) The authors, title and full bibliographic details are given
- (b) The content is not changed in any way
- (c) A hyperlink and/or URL are given for the original metadata page
- (d) Respect authors rights

Content and metadata policies

7. (1) Works should be submitted to the department by authors or on their behalf. Works will be uploaded into the IR by the department attachés or librarians.

(2) In the case of multiple authors:

- (a) At least one author should be a university affiliate
- (b) The submitting author should provide a written permission from other authors to upload the work in the IR

(3) Authors are responsible for the validity and originality of the uploaded work

(4) All submitted works will only be vetted for abiding by these policies

(5) All works should be supplied with metadata like author name, publisher and year of publication

(6) Some full text works uploaded in the IR may be classified and may have special usage regulations

(7) Dublin Core vocabulary terms will be used for all metadata

(8) The metadata may be re-used in any medium without prior permission for not-for-profit purposes provided mentioning the Open Archives Initiative Identifier or the main metadata URL in addition to mentioning the university IR as “KhartoumSpace IR, University of Khartoum institutional repository”.

(9) The metadata must not be re-used in any medium for commercial purposes without formal permission from the university or on its behalf.

Preservation Policy

8. (1) The author may withdraw the work or substitute it under the following conditions:
 - (a) Mistakes were discovered
 - (b) Work duplicate uploaded
- (2) A proven copyright violation or plagiarism or other legally accepted reasons for withdrawal
- (3) Works may be withdrawn from the IR and uploaded in a Closed Access Achieve if necessary
- (4) The university may withdraw works from the IR for professional and administrative reasons also
- (5) Withdrawn items are not deleted per se, but are removed from public view. Their identifiers/URLs are retained indefinitely and will continue to point to 'tombstone' citations, to avoid broken links and to retain item histories.
- (6) Withdrawn works will have information describing that it was withdrawn due to:
 - (a) Based on a written removal order by the author
 - (b) The university ordered the removal of the work
 - (c) Jurisdiction order
- (7) In the event of KhartoumSpace IR being closed down, the database will be transferred to another appropriate archive after the Senate approval

Intellectual property policies (IPP)

9. (1) The IR will be managed in agreement with the university and the national IPPs
- (2) Authors rights and publishers policies will be respected
- (3) Works with proved violation of IPP will be withdrawn immediately
- (4) Authors should submit the following for the work to be uploaded in the IR: 1) a signed non-exclusive agreement ([appendix 1](#)); 2) a copy of the permission letter ([appendix 2](#)) and 3) the original obtained license

Quality control

10. Some works will be evaluated by specialists before being uploaded to the IR

Regular review

11. This policy will be revised every four years by the committee in collaboration with the department and appropriate administrations at the university

Responsibility

12. The university, administrations, faculties and department holds no responsibility for mistakes in the works available in the IR. They do not pledge that all information there are correct also.

Final provisions

13. The non-exclusive agreement (appendix 1) and the permission letter (appendix 2) are original parts of this policy

Effective from:

Professor Ahmed Mohamed Suleiman, Vice Chancellor

Signature:

University stamp:

Appendix 1

Non-exclusive deposition Agreement

This Agreement purpose is to deposit all works prepared by university affiliates in all disciplines in the KhartoumSpace IR and hence help the university to achieve its mission as a pioneer institution.

To achieve this, the university signed this non-exclusive agreement with the author or those signing on her/his behalf. The author agreed, as the owner of the scholarly work entitled:

.....
.....

To deposit it in the KhartoumSpace IR according to the following rules:

1. I am , the owner of the previously mentioned work, agree to deposit it in the university IR to make it accessible publically according to the university regulations. I still hold the rights though to publish it elsewhere. I also agree that this work will be available in the IR even after I leave the university.
2. As the copyrights holder, I pledge the originality of this work and that it does not infringe any intellectual property policy
3. The university have the right to digitally modernize the work for a better readability
4. To withdraw the work, the department agreement will be obtained
5. The university have the right to permanently publish the uploaded work and its abstract for the public via any digital medium
6. The university have the right to digitally store, transform, translate or copy the work for preservation purposes
7. The department should provide works' metadata and documentation in public catalogues
8. The university may withdraw the work from the IR for professional and administrative reasons or in the case of proved violation of a third party rights
9. The university is not responsible for taking legal actions on behalf of the depositor or the rights holder in cases of intellectual property violation or other violations

10. The university is not committed to reproduce, publish or present the work in the same digital format submitted initially
11. In case that the university suffer by any means due to false information I gave, I pledge to reimburse the university

Depositor name:

Faculty\ School\ Institute\ Centre:

Department:.....

Signature:

Date:.....

On behalf of the DC Department:

Job description:

Signature:

Date:

Stamp:

Appendix 2

Permission letter

Dear Publisher,

As the rights holder, I/we request your permission to deposit a copy of the work mentioned below in the Repository of University of Khartoum, (<http://KhartoumSpace.uofk.edu:8080/jspui/>); which has been established with a view to enable the affiliates of the University to disseminate their scholarly work to the public; freely and without any financial gains, in line with the Creative commons attribution, non-commercial, no derivative works (4.0) license <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>. Works are deposited in the IR with reference to their full bibliographic details, metadata and links:

Title of the Book/Article/Conference Paper:

Journal:

Author/Co-Authors:

Publisher, address, year of publishing:

Pages:

ISBN/ISSN:

I'd be grateful if you would give permission for the use stated above. Please would you assist me by including the following in your reply:

- Confirmation that you are the rights holder
- Confirmation that permission has been granted
- Which version of the paper I may include
- Any other conditions that apply (e.g. must acknowledge the copyright holder)

Kind regards

Name:

Address:

Signature:

Date: